

REACTION OF ALDEHYDES AND AMINES WITH 8-QUINOLINOL

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Several 7- α -anilino-benzyl-8-quinolinols have been synthesised by a Mannich type of reaction between aldehydes, amines and 8-quinolinol with a view to studying their amoebicidal activity, and as precipitants for metal ions.

An unusually simple Mannich type of reaction has been reported to occur with aniline, benzaldehyde and 8-quinolinol, yielding 7- α -anilinobenzyl-8-quinolinol (Pirrone, *Gazzetta*, 1940, 70, 520; 1941, 71, 320).

These products (A) of reaction are compounds of the chelating type and are of interest as possible analytical reagents and for possible amoebicidal activity. Easy manipulation of the reaction, coupled with the potential usefulness of the products, has led several workers (Phillips *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4306; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 907) to explore its possibilities further.

In this paper the work has been extended, and the products from a number of aromatic primary amines and substituted aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes with 8-quinolinol are reported. Simple and poly-substituted aldehydes and amines have been used to study the effect of different substituents on the course of the reaction.

The reaction was carried out with benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, crotonaldehyde, heptaldehyde, *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 6-bromo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with the aromatic primary amines, *o*- and *p*-anisidines, 4-chloro-2-nitroaniline, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloroanilines, 1:3:4-xylydine, *p*-phenetidine, *m*- and *p*-nitroanilines and anthranilic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

The preparation of the compounds was carried out according to the procedure recommended by Phillips *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). Equimolar (or mole) proportions of the aldehyde and the amine were dissolved in sufficient (95%) ethanol to just dissolve the Schiff's base,

which separated out. To this 0.01 mole of 8-quinolinol was added, and the mixture stopped and left to stand at room temperature for 100 days. The precipitated product was removed by filtration and recrystallised from ethanol. The insoluble products were purified by repeated washings with alcohol. Acetone and glacial acetic acid were found to be unsuitable for crystallisation.

The time required for the first sign of precipitation to occur was recorded in each case (Table II). Precipitation continued slowly for many days after this time. Refluxing was normally without any effect on the speed of reaction, but in one instance, (I), the formation of the compound was facilitated.

Products were not obtained in 100 days' time from benzaldehyde with *p*-anisidine, 4-chloro-2-nitroaniline and *p*-phenetidine. Using salicylaldehyde, heptaldehyde or crotonaldehyde with *p*-nitroaniline, *p*-phenetidine, 4-chloro-2-nitroaniline, *o*-chloraniline, 1:3:4-xylydine, *p*-anisidine and anthranilic acid, the desired products could not be obtained.

The compounds can be represented by the general structural formula (A) (*vide supra*).

TABLE I
Substituted 7-*α*-anilino-8-quinolins.

No.	R ₁ .	R ₂ .	Formula.	M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.
I	C ₆ H ₅ -	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl	114°	30%	6.9	7.77
II	C ₆ H ₅ -	<i>m</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ ON ₂	140°	15	7.3	7.91
III	C ₆ H ₅ -	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl	128°	50	7.2	7.77
IV	C ₆ H ₅ -	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	145°	85	10.7	11.30
V	<i>m</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₁ N ₂	240°	90	10.2	10.85
VI	<i>m</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	102°	30	7.2	7.43
VII	<i>m</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	<i>m</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₁ N ₂	158°	40	10.3	10.85
VIII	<i>m</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂	172°	38	6.9	7.52
IX	6-Br- <i>m</i> .OH.C ₆ H ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₁ N ₂ Br	193°	20	8.7	9.01
X	CH ₃ (CH ₃) ₂ CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃	103°	12	10.6	11.08
XI	<i>o</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl-2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	175°	25	9.3	9.96

Spot Tests.—Colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid, concentrated nitric acid and 1% ferric chloride are spot tests for these products of reaction (Phillips *et al.*, *loc.cit.*). The first two of these, however, are not characteristic. Both were found to be positive in the case of the Schiff's base from salicylaldehyde and *p*-nitroaniline and only the 1% ferric chloride test responded negative. On the other hand, (VIII) reacted positive only to the ferric chloride test. Thus in the characterisation of these products, the ferric chloride test is the specific one, while the other two are secondary.

TABLE II

No.	Time for first sign of ppt.	Colour reaction with		
		Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	Conc. HNO ₃ .	1% FeCl ₃ .
I	68 days	Red	Yellow	Green
II	45	"	Yellow (persists)	"
III	35	"	Yellow	"
IV	8	"	"	"
V	1½	"	"	"
VI	39	"	"	"
VII	38	Dark brown	"	"
VIII	8	Yellow	"	Green black
IX	22	Deep brown	"	Green
X	45	Yellow	"	"
XI	65	Red	"	"

CONCLUSIONS

Compounds containing a nitro group were yellow while all others were tinged or colorless.

The study yielded the following further conclusions :

(1) The most active amine in all cases was found to be *para*-nitroaniline. Comparatively speaking, the order of reactivity of the nitroanilines is *para* > *meta* > *ortho*.

(2) The methoxy group in the *ortho*-position to the amino group disposes more favourably than that in the *para*-position, towards the speed of reaction.

(3) Benzaldehyde was found to be more reactive than its substituted derivatives.

(4) *m*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde gave products with a number of amines. Of the three substituted hydroxybenzaldehydes, *meta*-isomer was found to be the most reactive.

(5) In the case of 6-bromo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, the bromine in the *ortho*-position decreased the rate of reaction.

(6) In the cases studied, it has been observed that the effect of introducing substituents in the aldehyde part is to decrease the yield and rate of reaction (cf. benzaldehyde, *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 6-bromo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with *p*-nitroaniline and 1:3:4-xylidine).